

Food Adoption, Transformation Strategies, And Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

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ABSTRACT

Published Online: January 30, 2026

This study examined the relationship between food adoption, transformation strategies, and customer satisfaction in selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna. Using a descriptive-correlational design, data were collected from 223 customers selected through simple random sampling across four restaurants. A validated, researcher-made questionnaire measured the five dimensions of food adoption: culture, tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy; the two dimensions of transformation strategies: menu innovation and ambiance; alongside with the levels of customer satisfaction. Results showed that overall food adoption was rated “High” (M = 3.06), with social bonding ranking highest (M = 3.17), followed by culture (M = 3.06), consumer preferences (M = 3.04), and both tradition and local economy ranking the lowest (M = 3.02). Overall transformation strategies were rated “High” (M = 3.06), with ambiance ranking highest (M = 3.16) and menu innovation ranking the lowest (M = 2.95). Customer satisfaction was rated “High” (M = 3.00). Pearson r correlation analysis indicated significant relationships: food adoption dimensions correlated moderately with transformation strategies dimension of menu innovation ($r = .185$ to $.283$, $p < .01$). Food adoption dimension of tradition correlated moderately with transformation strategies dimension of ambiance ($r = .164$, $p < .05$). Food adoption dimensions showed a moderately positive correlation with customer satisfaction ($r = .158$ to $.346$, $p < .01$, $p < .05$). Transformation strategies dimensions presented a significant relationship with customer satisfaction ($r = .207$ to $.324$, $p < .01$). Findings confirm that high levels of specific food adoption dimensions are concordant to high levels transformation strategies dimensions and customer satisfaction. High levels of transformation strategies dimensions are also concordant to a high level of customer satisfaction. The study recommends to focus on staff training, customer feedback engagement, and acquiring an extensive understanding of Korean and Filipino culture for sustained business growth.

KEYWORDS:

Food Adoption, Transformation Strategies, Customer Satisfaction, Samgyeopsal Restaurants, Korean-Filipino, Food Adoption Behavior Model Correlational Study

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*Cite this Article: Dr. Christian D. Tongko, Chester M. Cajumban, Kian Lyxander F. Muñoz, Ma. Luisa G. Gomez, Marlo D. Resano (2026). *Food Adoption, Transformation Strategies, And Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 6(1), 90-101*

INTRODUCTION

Samgyeopsal is a South Korean dish of thinly sliced pork belly, generally served raw and cooked by the diner on a tabletop grill (Lam, 2024). This fascination with *samgyeopsal* has led to the creation of Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants that cater to this Korean food item in the Philippines which further integrates it into the Filipino gastronomic culture.

Rajan (2023), states that food adoption can occur because of trade routes, colonialism, and migration. These factors can introduce new food items and cooking methods

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which the host region will then absorb. Due to social norms, needs, habits, convictions, deliberations, and compromises, an individual may choose to adopt food into one’s culture (Borghini, 2019).

Transformation strategies are changes in the intrinsic (sensory and food-related qualities) and extrinsic (non-food) qualities of food that accompany the advancement of societies. Economic cycles, natural calamities, and diseases, such as the previous COVID-19 pandemic, have caused a transformation in the present food systems, particularly in the Philippines (Palo et al., 2020).

Customer satisfaction is defined by Hamzah and Shamsudin (2020) as an indication of “how well the product use experience compares to the buyer’s value expectations.” It is also defined by Uslu and Eren (2020) as a “judgment that a product or service feature, or the product or service itself,

METHODS

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between food adoption, transformation strategies, and customer satisfaction in selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna. A descriptive-correlational is the method wherein it describes variables and measures the extent of their relationships through what occurs between and among the variables (Aprecia et al., 2022).

The population of the study are the customers of the four selected *samgyeopsal* restaurants. The average daily foot traffic was the basis for the population size, totaling to 530 customers. A sample size of 223 respondents was derived from a Raosoft calculator with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. The actual selection of willing respondents was done through simple random sampling. Respondents were approached during or after dining, informed of the study’s purpose, and assured of voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to ensure data accuracy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of the study on customer service, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty

1. Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 1 Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Culture

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants have adopted Korean culture and can be	3.25	Very High	3
2. Both Filipino and Korean culture are equally represented in	2.76	High	7
3. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants play an important role in promoting	3.34	Very High	2

provided (or is providing) a pleasurable level of consumption fulfillment, including the levels of under or over-fulfillment.”

There are limited researches focused on food adoption, transformation strategies, and customer satisfaction, limited studies focus on Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna. This study examined the relationship between food adoption, transformation strategies, and customer satisfaction in selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants. Utilizing the Food Adoption Behavior Model, Theory of Planned Behavior, and Expectation Disconfirmation Theory, it explores how culture, tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, local economy affect menu innovation and ambiance and in turn, impact customer satisfaction. Findings aim to highlight the critical role of local cuisines and consumer preferences in the effective adoption of foreign culinary traditions and the process in which they transform due to various external and internal factors.

A researcher-made questionnaire was the main research instrument used. It had three sections focused on the level of food adoption (culture, tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy), transformation strategies (menu innovation and ambiance), and level of customer satisfaction. Content and face validation were conducted by a research adviser, statistician, and hospitality management expert. A reliability test using Cronbach’s Alpha reflected a valid and acceptable range of internal consistency or reliability across all constructs. Data collection was conducted with permission from each respective restaurant management and the College Dean. The researchers administered the questionnaires, providing instructions before the respondents completed them. Weighted mean was used to determine the level of food adoption, transformation strategies, customer satisfaction; Pearson r was employed to test the significance of the relationships among variables at 0.01 and 0.05 significance levels to ensure accuracy and reliability of findings.

in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. The results are organized according to the study’s research questions and hypotheses, supported by statistical data, relevant literature, and interpretation.

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4. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants help to introduce Korean culture to	3.55	Very High	1
5. I view <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to be the easiest way to have an	3.05	High	4
6. I have become more informed of Korean culture through	2.83	High	6
7. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to be exposed to Korean culture.	2.74	High	8
8. I can use <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants as a way to make others become	2.95	High	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.06	High	

As shown in Table 1, the overall level of food adoption of *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of culture, was “High” with an average weighted mean of 3.06. This means that the respondents see *samgyeopsal* restaurants to be an introduction to Korean culture. Indicator 4 ranked first, followed by Indicator 3, Indicator 1 ranked third, Indicator 5 ranked fourth, Indicator 8 ranked fifth. Additionally, Indicator 6 ranked sixth, Indicator 2 ranked seventh, and Indicator 7 ranked last.

These findings are supported by the study done by Ong, Prasetyo, Manguray, et al. (2023) wherein Korean influence, particularly culture, plays a factor in how food is adopted by Filipinos. In addition, Pineda (2024) and Wehmeyer (2021) noted similarities between Filipino culture and Korean culture; this can also contribute to the high levels of food adoption in terms of culture.

Table 2 Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Tradition

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants show the blending of Korean and Filipino traditions.	2.81	High	8
2. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants provide knowledge about Korean tradition.	3.12	High	2
3. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants show Filipino traditions and mix them with Korean traditions through the food.	2.86	High	6
4. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants show the “Filipino hospitality” with Korean traditions such as food sharing.	3.10	High	4
5. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to have an idea about Korean traditions.	2.82	High	7
6. I feel comfortable with my Filipino identity while dining at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants.	3.24	High	1
7. Dining at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants made me appreciate Korean traditions.	3.09	High	5
8. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants have encouraged me to respect and learn more about Korean and Filipino traditions.	3.11	High	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.02	High	

As presented in Table 2, the overall level of food adoption in *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City,

Laguna, in terms of tradition was “High” with an average weighted mean of 3.02. This means that the respondents are

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comfortable with their Filipino identity while dining at *samgyeopsal* restaurants. Indicator 6 ranked first, followed by Indicator 2, Indicator 8 ranked third, Indicator 4 ranked fourth, Indicator 7 ranked fifth. Indicator 3, Indicator 5, and Indicator 1 ranked sixth, seventh, and eighth, respectively.

These findings are supported by the research done by Rocillo-Aquino et al. (2021) wherein traditional foods are concepts of the culture that produced them and can be handed down from one generation to another. This coincides with what Nepomuceno (2021) deemed as the “Filipino identity” – absorbing other traditions, amalgamating them, and infusing them to be a part of their own.

Table 3 Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Consumer Preferences

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are an easy way to get protein and vegetables into my diet.	2.91	High	7
2. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because they are trendy.	2.74	High	8
3. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because of the different ways I can enjoy eating meat.	3.34	Very High	2
4. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to relieve my daily stresses.	2.94	High	6
5. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to enjoy the blending of Korean and Filipino flavors.	2.96	High	5
6. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because I can cook my own food.	3.02	High	4
7. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because they provide value for my money.	3.03	High	3
8. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because of the good food quality.	3.39	Very High	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.04	High	

As shown in Table 3, the overall level of food adoption in *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of consumer preferences was “High” with an average weighted mean of 3.04. This means that the respondents eat at *samgyeopsal* restaurants because of the good food quality. Indicator 8 ranked first, followed by Indicator 3 while Indicator 7 ranked third. Indicator 6 ranked fourth, Indicator 5 ranked fifth, Indicator 4 ranked sixth, Indicator 1 ranked seventh, and Indicator 2 ranked eighth.

These findings are similar to the study done by Ong, Prasetyo, Esteller, et al. (2023) where they found that consumers pick the *samgyeopsal* restaurant they will dine at depending on their preferences, mostly referring to the food quality and food options. Additionally, this is also what has been observed in the research study conducted by Ong, Prasetyo, Manguray, et al. (2023) where consumers chose to eat at *samgyeopsal* restaurants because of their preferences such as causing their moods to be enlivened, provide a sense of relief, and have a great overall experience.

Table 4 Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Social Bonding

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Eating at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants is a way to bond with other people.	3.26	Very High	3
2. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants with my friends or family.	3.39	Very High	1
3. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants because I can share food with others.	3.27	Very High	2
4. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants encourage social bonding.	3.10	High	5

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5. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are ideal for parties or events.	3.14	High	4
6. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants highlight the practice of social eating.	3.07	High	6
7. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are an option for dates.	3.05	High	8
8. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are more suitable for large groups of people than other types of restaurants.	3.06	High	7
Average Weighted Mean	3.17	High	

As shown in Table 4, the overall level of food adoption in selected Korean- Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of social bonding, attained an average weighted mean of 3.17, which is interpreted as “High.” This means that the respondents prefer to eat at *samgyeopsal* restaurants with their friends or family. Indicator 2 ranked first, followed by Indicator 3 and Indicator 1 ranked third. Indicator 5 ranked fourth, Indicator 4 ranked fifth, Indicator 6 ranked sixth, Indicator 8 ranked seventh, and Indicator 7 ranked eighth.

These findings are similar to what Gregersen and Gillath (2020) found in their research which they concluded that food sharing and offering food to others are linked to closeness and facilitate and strengthen social bonds. In addition, these findings are also corroborated by Higgs and Ruddock’s (2020) wherein social eating has a powerful and noticeable effect on what and how much people eat.

Table 5 Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Local Economy

Indicators	Weighted	Interpretation	Rank
1. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are profitable.	3.05	High	4
2. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants have decent and justified pricing.	3.14	High	2
3. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants can contribute to the wealth of the community where it is located.	3.24	High	1
4. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants have influenced me to purchase more Korean-related products.	2.92	High	6
5. My money is well spent when eating at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants.	2.90	High	7
6. I find <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to be approachable because of their prices.	3.01	High	5
7. I eat at <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants to save money on expensive food items.	2.79	High	8
8. <i>Samgyeopsal</i> restaurants are appropriate for anybody regardless of social class.	3.08	High	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.02	High	

As shown in Table 5, the overall level of food adoption of *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of local economy, was “High” with an average weighted mean of 3.02. This means that *samgyeopsal* restaurants can contribute to the wealth of the community where it is located. Indicator 3 ranked first, followed by Indicator 2, and Indicator 8 ranked third. Indicator 1 ranked fourth, Indicator 6 ranked fifth, Indicator 4 ranked sixth, Indicator 5 ranked seventh, and Indicator 7 ranked eighth.

These findings are supported by Balita (2024), wherein it was found that restaurants greatly contribute to the economic health of a location where they are located. This is also substantiated by the statement of Walker (2021) that people see restaurants as a different kind of necessity, a “well-earned reward” for their efforts. Hence, its importance to the local community and its involvement in the growth of the community’s fiscal properties.

Table 6 Summary Table of Food Adoption of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Indicators	Weighted	Interpretation	Rank
Culture	3.06	High	2
Tradition	3.02	High	4.5
Consumer Preferences	3.04	High	3
Social Bonding	3.17	High	1
Local Economy	3.02	High	4.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.06	High	

Table 6 presents the summary of the food adoption indicators with the overall weighted mean is 3.06 and interpreted as “High” across all indicators. This indicates that food adoption occurs in Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants. Among the indicators, food adoption in terms of social bonding had the highest weighted mean of 3.17,

interpreted as “High,” and ranked first. Culture followed with a weighted mean of 3.06, also interpreted as “High,” ranking second. Consumer preferences ranked third with a weighted mean of 3.04, interpreted as “High,” Lastly, tradition and local economy shared the fourth rank with a weighted mean of 3.02, interpreted as “High.”

2. Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 7 Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Menu Innovation

Indicators	Weighted	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant balances Korean influence with Filipino culture.	2.75	High	7.5
2. The restaurant introduces new dishes that show Korean and Filipino flavors.	2.82	High	6
3. The restaurant listens to feedback to provide new food items to customers.	2.75	High	7.5
4. The restaurant uses trending Korean food items and transforms it for the Filipino market.	2.95	High	5
5. The restaurant transforms Korean food to fit the Filipino taste.	3.00	High	3
6. The restaurant has a unique menu that cannot be found in other <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurants.	3.10	High	2
7. The restaurant has new food items that are still relevant to their brand.	2.99	High	4
8. The restaurant creates new food items that have a Korean influence but can still be enjoyed by Filipinos.	3.21	High	1
Average Weighted Mean	2.95	High	

As shown in Table 7, the overall level of transformation strategy in selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of menu innovation was “High” with an average weighted mean of 2.95. This means that *samgyeopsal* restaurants creates new food items that have a Korean influence but can still be enjoyed by Filipinos. Indicator 8 ranked first, followed by Indicator 6, and Indicator 5 ranked third. Indicator 7 ranked fourth, Indicator 4 ranked fifth, Indicator 2 ranked sixth, and Indicator 1 and 3 shared the last rank.

These findings support Rasa’s (2019) study, that menu innovation is a widely used transformation strategy to remain competitive in the food and beverage industry and as the results show, can be found in a variety of restaurants in the Philippines, particularly in Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants. The results also support Mutlu et al.’s (2022) study as menu innovation indeed involves the introduction of new food items through the understanding of trends and preferences.

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Table 8 Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Ambiance

Indicators	Weighted	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant has appropriate lighting for customers.	3.23	High	3
2. The restaurant plays music that is both Korean and Filipino.	3.09	High	6
3. The restaurant is clean and follows food safety regulations and standards.	3.20	High	5
4. The restaurant disperses the heat from the grills through their ventilation.	3.30	Very High	1
5. The restaurant has courteous employees that provide a great experience for customers.	3.21	High	4
6. The restaurant has windows to let natural light in.	3.24	High	2
7. The restaurant has appropriate decorations that mix Korean and Filipino influences.	2.96	High	8
8. The restaurant has an appealing scent that attracts customers.	3.02	High	7
Average Weighted Mean	3.16	High	

As shown in Table 8, the overall level of transformation strategy in selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, in terms of ambiance was “High” with an average weighted mean of 3.16. This means that *samgyeopsal* restaurants disperses the heat from the grills through their ventilation. Indicator 4 ranked first, followed by Indicator 6, and Indicator 1 ranked third. Indicator 5 ranked fourth, Indicator 3 ranked fifth, Indicator 2 ranked sixth, Indicator 8 ranked seventh, and Indicator 7 ranked eighth.

These findings show that ambiance is a significant element that allows restaurants to be competitive and that it supports the conclusions derived from Anaam’s (2022) research that light, sound, heat, smell, air flows, and touch, to name a few, contribute to an establishment’s overall ambiance and has an effect on the consumer. In addition, the results share similarities with the results of the study by Kement et al. (2021) where it was found that ambiance played a significant role in paying more positively and revisiting intentions.

Table 9 Summary Table of Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Menu Innovation	2.95	High	2
Ambiance	3.16	High	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.06	High	

As shown in Table 9, the transformation strategies in terms of menu innovation and ambiance has an overall weighted mean of 3.06, interpreted as “High.” This indicates that transformation strategies are present in Korean-Filipino

samgyeopsal restaurants. Ambiance ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.16, which is interpreted as “High.” In contrast, menu innovation had a weighted mean of 2.95, also interpreted as “High,” and ranked second.

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3. Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 10 Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Indicators	Weighted	Interpretation	Rank
1. The food quality in the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant is of the highest quality.	2.78	High	8
2. The staff are approachable and treat me and other customers with patience and respect.	3.02	High	5
3. The <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant met my needs and expectations.	3.00	High	6
4. I feel satisfied with the products and services offered by the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant.	3.05	High	3
5. I feel satisfied with the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant’s staff with their prompt response and service.	2.98	High	7
6. I would recommend the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant to other people.	3.06	High	1.5
7. I gained a good and positive impression of the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant.	3.04	High	4
8. I would revisit the <i>samgyeopsal</i> restaurant again.	3.06	High	1.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.00	High	

As presented in Table 10, the overall level of customer satisfaction of selected Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna, was "High" with an average weighted mean of 3.00. This means that the respondents would recommend the *samgyeopsal* restaurant and revisit again. Indicator 6 and 8 share the first ranking, followed by Indicator 4 which placed at third. Indicator 7 ranked fourth, Indicator 2 ranked fifth, Indicator 3 ranked sixth, Indicator 5 ranked seventh, and Indicator 1 ranked eighth. These findings share similarities with the conclusions derived by Shin and Yu

(2020) in their study where the quality of the physical environment, food, and service has an effect on customer satisfaction.

These results also support the outcomes of Hallencreutz and Parmler’s (2019) study on customer satisfaction as achieving a high level of customer satisfaction can lead to a stronger brand image, protection of current market share, increased customer loyalty, decreased customer complaints, and strengthened financial performance.

4. Relationship Between Food Adoption and Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 11 Relationship between Food Adoption and Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Menu Innovation

Food Adoption Indicators	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Culture	0.116	0.083	Not Significant
Tradition	0.283	0.000	Significant
Consumer Preferences	0.191	0.004	Significant
Social Bonding	0.185	0.006	Significant
Local Economy	0.195	0.003	Significant
<i>0.01 level of significance</i>			

As shown in the table above, the relationship between food adoption in terms of tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy and transformation

strategies in menu innovation resulted in a significant relationship. Pearson r-values of 0.283, 0.191, 0.185, and 0.195 were obtained. All of the p-values that were obtained were

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lower than the 0.01 level of significance which showed that there is a significant relationship between food adoption in terms of tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy and transformation strategies in terms of menu innovation. A high level of tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy means that there is also a high level of menu innovation. However, for the relationship between food adoption in terms of culture and transformation strategies in terms of menu innovation, a Pearson r-value of 0.116 and a p-value of 0.083, which was higher than the 0.01 level of significance, were obtained. This denoted that there is

no significant relationship between culture and menu innovation.

These results correlate to the conclusions and findings of Nepomuceno (2021) and Gregersen and Gillath (2020). Whereby they discussed that Filipinos tend to adopt other traditions and amalgamate them together with performing interpersonal behaviors regarding food, respectively. However, the lack of significant relationship between culture and menu innovation is contrasting result from the studies performed by Ong, Prasetyo, Manguray, et al. (2023) where they found that culture also affects the creation of menus in Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants.

Table 12 Relationship between Food Adoption and Transformation Strategies of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna: Ambiance

Food Adoption Indicators	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Culture	0.082	0.225	Not Significant
Tradition	0.164	0.014	Significant
Consumer Preferences	0.066	0.323	Not Significant
Social Bonding	0.075	0.263	Not Significant
Local Economy	0.102	0.130	Not Significant
<i>0.05 level of significance</i>			

As shown in the table above, the relationship between food adoption in terms of tradition and transformation strategies in terms of ambiance resulted in a Pearson r-value of 0.164 and a p-value of 0.014 which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance, conveying that there is a significant relationship between food adoption in terms of tradition and transformation strategies in terms of ambiance. A high level of tradition means that there is also a high level of ambiance. Inversely, the relationship between food adoption in terms of culture, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy and transformation strategies in terms of ambiance reflected Pearson r-values of 0.082, 0.066, 0.075, and 0.102, respectively. In addition, p-values of 0.225, 0.323, 0.263, and 0.130, respectively, which were higher than the 0.05 level of

significance were obtained. This showed that there is no significant relationship between culture, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy and ambiance.

The results indicating the presence of a significant relationship of food adoption in terms of tradition and transformation strategies in terms of ambiance is supported by the findings of Tupas & Lee (2020). The lack of a significant relationship between consumer preferences and social bonding and ambiance contrast the conclusions by Barone (2021) about the adoption of food with regards to socialization and the environment where an individual reside. It also contrasts Byrne’s (2020) findings that food adoption can occur with respect to an individual’s preferences and external environment.

5. Relationship between Food Adoption and Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 13 Relationship between Food Adoption and Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino *Samgyeopsal* Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Food Adoption Indicators	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Culture	0.229	0.009**	Significant
Tradition	0.158	0.019*	Significant

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Consumer Preferences	0.240	0.000**	Significant
Social Bonding	0.006	0.927	Not Significant
Local Economy	0.346	0.000**	Significant
<i>**0.01 level of significance</i>			
<i>*0.05 level of significance</i>			

As shown in the table above, the relationship between food adoption in terms of culture, tradition, consumer preferences, and local economy and customer satisfaction resulted in Pearson r-values of 0.229, 0.158, 0.240, and 0.346, respectively. All of the p-values obtained were lower than the set levels of significance which showed that there is a significant relationship between culture, tradition, consumer preferences, local economy, and customer satisfaction. A high level of culture, tradition, consumer preferences, and local economy means that there will also be a high level of customer satisfaction. Inversely, the relationship between food adoption in terms of social

bonding and customer satisfaction resulted in a Pearson r-value of 0.006. A p-value of 0.927 was obtained which was higher than the 0.05 level of significance which showed that there is no significant relationship between social bonding and customer satisfaction.

The results showing a lack of significant relationship between food adoption in terms of social bonding and customer satisfaction contrasts with the results of the study by Higgs and Ruddock (2020) wherein they concluded that social influence has a pervasive effect on people along with its impact on food choices.

6. Relationship between Transformation Strategies and Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Table 14 Relationship between Transformation Strategies and Customer Satisfaction of Selected Korean-Filipino Samgyeopsal Restaurants in Santa Rosa City, Laguna

Transformation Strategies Indicators	Pearson r	p value	Interpretation
Menu Innovation	0.324	0.000	Significant
Ambiance	0.207	0.002	Significant
<i>0.01 level of significance</i>			

As shown in the table above, the relationship between transformation strategies in terms of menu innovation and ambiance, and customer satisfaction resulted in Pearson r-values of 0.324 and 0.207, respectively. All of the p-values obtained were lower than the 0.01 level of significance which showed that there is a significant relationship between menu innovation and ambiance and customer satisfaction. A high level of menu innovation and ambiance means that there will also be a high level of customer satisfaction.

These results are correlated with the study findings of Güzel and Baş (2020) where they concluded that physical environmental factors affects customer satisfaction. In addition, these results are also supported by Anaam’s study (2022) that showed that ambiance does have an effect on customer satisfaction and Mutlu et al.’s (2019) study that relayed that menu innovation indeed has an effect on customer satisfaction as well.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the findings of the study conducted, customers choose to eat at Korean-Filipino *samgyeopsal* restaurants because of the opportunity to socially bond with their families and friends. Due to the presence of proper ventilation, customers have felt satisfied with *samgyeopsal* restaurants. Moreover, it was found that tradition, consumer preferences, social bonding, and local economy has a significant correlation to menu innovation. Tradition has a significant correlation to ambiance. Culture, tradition, consumer preferences, and local economy has a significant correlation to customer satisfaction. Menu innovation and ambiance has a significant correlation with customer satisfaction. There is no significant correlation with culture and menu innovation together culture, consumer preferences, social bonding, local economy and ambiance.

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To improve the level of food adoption, it is recommended to that *samgyeopsal* owners and managers in Santa Rosa City, Laguna to perform extensive research on Korean cultures and traditions and how it can be implemented to the different aspects of their establishment. To provide better ambiance, appropriate decorations or equipment that showcase Korean culture and promote socialization while continually listening and engaging with customer feedback is recommended. To improve customer satisfaction, it is recommended for the management of the *samgyeopsal* restaurants to conduct training seminars for their employees, listening to customer feedback, and a collaborative effort during team meetings on what aspects of the business should be enhanced. The lack of a significant relationship between food adoption in terms of culture and menu innovation; food adoption in terms of culture, consumer references, social bonding, and local economy and ambiance can be used to perform an in-depth analysis on how to show Korean and Filipino culture when creating new dishes to add to the menu.

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